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Támogató:

Megjelenés: évente. A kiadvány egyetemi oktatók által minősített munkákat tartalmaz. A recenzensek kijelölése a tudományos folyóiratok kritériumait meghatározó szabállyal összhangban valósul meg (Službeni glasnik, Szerb Köztársaság, 79/05. szám).

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INTERCULTURAL VOCATIONAL EXCHANGES OF YOUNG PEOPLE AS A MODEL OF LEARNING

*A fiatalok interkulturális szakmai cseréje mint tanulási
modell*

*Interkulturelne razmene mladih profesionalaca kao model
učenja*

1. Intercultural learning

„In the increasingly global society we live in, it seems more clear than ever that we learn how to communicate with our neighbors in an adaptable and sensitive manner, and it is valuable to know that studying abroad is one opportunity that can help in that endeavor.“ (T.R. Williams, 2005)

In the Intercultural Learning T-Kit (2000), one of the biggest challenges of intercultural learning is that there is no clearly defined educational discipline known as „intercultural learning”. It is described as learning about different cultures through interaction with members of diverse cultures. Thus, intercultural learning takes place within the framework of non-formal education, as part of the curriculum or as a spontaneous consequence of the program for achieving another educational aim and includes intercultural learning.

In the past, education was based on social equity, reduction of diversity and work on social integration. In the current socio-political context, dealing with diversity becomes the primary task. Culture is part of a group or people whose members are proud and represent it as traditional characteristics and specific social behavior. Culture defines and distinguishes one nation from others. (Dolo, 2000) People manage their activities and values only if they are in harmony with the social behavior. If we accept people, we accept their cultural and spiritual environment. (Knežević-Florić, 2005)

Based on the General Declaration on Cultural Diversity, UNESCO (2005) Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions was endorsed. According to the Convention, cultural diversity encompasses the ways in which cultural

groups and societies express themselves. These expressions are transmitted within and between cultural groups, societies and manifest cultural heritage. Expressions transmit the diversity of cultures through different ways of artistic creativity, production, diffusion, distribution and enjoyment in cultural expressions. (Jovanov, 2013)

Intercultural learning helps us to understand cultural diversity. It is based on principles which include: openness to others, respect for diversity, mutual understanding, active tolerance, and respect for another culture, securing equal opportunities and combating discrimination.

Therefore, intercultural learning (Ouellet, 1991, according to Intercultural Learning T-kit, 2000), should strive to promote and develop a better understanding of cultures in modern society. Increased ability to communicate with people from different cultures could create flexible attitudes towards differences in society and set up greater willingness of people to actively engage in social interaction with people of other cultural backgrounds. In social interaction, the basic characteristics of human nature will be recognized as something people have in common.

Intercultural learning is also a process of personal development with an impact on society. It requires every one of us to know ourselves, so that we can understand others. This process is very challenging and involves working on deep-rooted beliefs. For this reason, intercultural learning, which is practiced within the framework of non-formal education, can play a significant role in the reexamination of myths and generate discussion among young people about how national identities are formed and how they are influenced by them.

The primary aspect of Bennett's definition of intercultural learning is the idea of context. Bennett, as an author, defining it as acquiring increased awareness of subjective cultural context and developing greater ability to interact sensitively and competently across cultural contexts.

Culture can be thought of as context in both the objective and subjective sense. Objective culture is the set of institutional, political and historical circumstances, and subject is a personal context of cultural self-awareness. Cultural self-awareness is a necessary precursor of intercultural learning. It involves recognizing cultural differences. If young people do not have a cultural self-awareness for their own culture, they will find it difficult to recognize and manage cultural differences. They may learn something about the target culture, but that kind of culture learning is different from intercultural learning. (Bennett, 2009) The intercultural experience of young people from the perspective of critical pedagogy in relation to intercultural learning must be through an interactive approach. Young people must be active subjects in their intercultural learning. (Milutinović, Zuković, 2008) In order to achieve cultural self-awareness, young people should have an engaging approach to the concept of intercultural learning. One of the engaged and active approaches is through Youth Exchange.

2. Previous research on Youth Exchange projects

The international commute have long been a part of education and universities include some version of knowledge of other cultures as a component of education. Studying abroad has often been considered as an experience reserved for the wealthy to demonstrate skills and qualities needed for success in today's world. (Rundstrom Williams, 2005)

A new trend in academics called outcome assessment has shifted the focus of education toward "competency-based education that stresses learner outcomes over teacher input" (Fantini, Arias-Galicia, & Guay, 2001, according to Rundstrom Williams, 2005). These assessments force educators to evaluate what students are learning, what skills they are developing, and how these skills translate into knowledge needed for jobs and for life.

Author T.R. Williams conducted a study focusing on identifying and measuring the improvement of intercultural communication skills as a possible outcome. Williams identified intercultural communication skills as one of the education outcomes needed for successful education.

In this study the two groups of students were selected as follows: The abroad group was the fall 2002 study abroad students at Texas Christian University (TCU). This group included students studying in Australia, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Mexico, the Netherlands,

Russia, Spain and the United Kingdom.

In the fall of 2002 study, two groups of students were selected; the students studying abroad and the students that stayed on campus at Texas Christian University (TCU). The abroad group included students studying in Australia, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Mexico, the Netherlands, Russia, Spain and the United Kingdom.

This study was initiated in an effort to better understand and quantify the benefits of study abroad in the context of a multicultural world and it was the first step in identifying and measuring intercultural communication skills of students. The conclusion was that students who study abroad showed a greater change in intercultural communication skills. Unexpectedly, the greater outcome of this study is the relationship of exposure to other cultures as a function of intercultural communication skills. This confirms that the experience of being abroad is not enough. Students must interact in the culture to receive the benefit of increased intercultural communication skills.

Koskinen and Tossavainen (2004) conducted a research to describe an international student exchange programme in the context of learning intercultural competence in nursing. Twelve Finnish nursing students participated in an exchange programme in the United Kingdom. They concluded that study abroad as a process of learning intercultural competence consisted of three ethno-categories: transition from one culture to another, adjustment to the difference and gaining intercultural sensitivity. (Koskinen&Tossavainen,2004) This study showed a problematic orientation phase (beginning of the exchanges) that involved stressful but rewarding adjustment to the intercultural differences. Particularly,

the students needed intercultural tutoring and mentoring to venture into encounters with local people, including direct client contacts, during their study abroad.

Based on research *Students of four decades* (Bachner and Zeutschel 2009a, according to Bennett, 2009) claim increased credibility for some of the common wisdom in study abroad: Homestays are reported to be an important part of the program; duration of the program is important – the longer the exchange, the greater its perceived impact, former participants are more likely to become involved in international peace and cooperation efforts.

3. Roots and context of youth exchange

International Youth Exchanges are specific and could have different roots for different organizers. In the western part of Europe first steps to establish structures for youth exchanges became part of foreign policy in the 1950's and was linked with the idea of reconciliation. In the eastern part of Europe, youth exchanges were mostly organized with the idea to promote solidarity between socialist societies. One important step for the development of youth exchanges in Europe was the foundation of the German French Youth Agency in 1963. This today provides funds for youth exchanges. Since the 1970's and 1980's new concepts have developed mostly in the framework of intercultural learning by the Erasmus+ Programme. (Zhukov&Schwieren, 2017)

At the European level, the first discussion regarding youth aspects started as part of the framework of the Council of Europe. In order to promote mobility and participation, the youth center in Strasbourg was founded and reports were published. In 1988, Youth for Europe, the first activity of the Youth Exchanges program was funded. The EU Commission and the national agencies became active partners to develop youth policies in the European framework throughout the period since. Today, it is the Erasmus+ Programme.

One of the aims of International Youth Exchange Erasmus+ Programme is to create a space for effective learning processes on a personal level with the following dimensions:

- discovering and deconstructing prejudice and stereotypes,
- reflecting participants' own behavior and attitudes,
- exploring perceptions to be open to differences,
- cultural sensibility - seeing diversity inside one culture and
- reflecting participants' own relationship with national culture (Zhukov&Schwieren, 2017)

The projects supported by this program have a strong international and intercultural dimension. They require cooperation with at least one or more partner from another country. Most projects include more than 3 countries. Participation in activities that gather young people from different countries are essential for conveying youth in different perspectives, teaching appreciation of diversity and creating an accepting environment.

The Erasmus+ Programme endorses multilingualism. (Program Guide, 2019) The promotion of language learning and linguistic diversity is one of the specific Erasmus+ Programme objectives. In the era of internationalization of working processes, the goal is that every citizen should learn at least two foreign languages. Although, English is most widely used as a working language in the Erasmus+ projects, international projects encourage learning other languages.

Definition of the youth exchanges that stated in the Erasmus+ Programme describes youth exchanges as an activity for groups of young people from two or more different countries. They live together, learn and have fun for up to 21 days. During the exchange, participants are supported by group leaders and together they carry out a working program. Methodology of the youth exchange is based on an interactive approach. It is a mixed structure of workshops, exercises, debates, role-plays, simulations and outdoor activities. Youth Exchanges allow young people to actively participate, develop own competencies, become aware of themed areas, discover new cultures, traditional habits, strengthen values like solidarity, democracy, friendship, etc. The learning process in youth exchanges is triggered by methods of nonformal education, mainly, participants learn through peer learning. Exchanges offer an international mobility experience and a good surrounding for discussing and learning about inclusion and diversity issues. (Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017, Erasmus+ Programme Guide, 2019)

The Erasmus+ projects promote and support in the fields of education, training, youth and sport for the period 2014-2020 (Erasmus+ Programme Guide, 2019). The program is helping socio-economic changes and key challenges that Europe will be facing in this decade, as well as supporting the implementation of the European policy agenda for growth, jobs, equity and social inclusion. The Erasmus+ Programme is seen as an investment in knowledge, skills and competencies from which individuals, institutions, organizations and society will benefit as a whole by contributing to growth and ensuring equity, prosperity and social inclusion in Europe and beyond.

In the field of youth, Erasmus+ supports the following main Actions:

Key Action 1: Mobility for young people and youth workers

Key Action 2: Capacity-building projects in the field of youth

Key Action 3: Involvement of young people and youth organizations from neighboring EU partner countries and the youth Structured Dialogue forum.

The specific objectives pursued by the Erasmus+ Programme in the field of youth are:

- to improve the level of key competencies and skills of young people,
- to support participation of youth with fewer opportunities,
- to promote participation in democratic life in Europe and the labor market, active citizenship, intercultural dialogue, social inclusion and solidarity,
- to increase learning mobility opportunities for young people,
- to foster quality improvements in youth work, in particular through enhanced cooperation between organizations in the youth field,

- to complement policy reforms at local, regional and national level and to support the development of knowledge and evidence-based youth policy,
- to recognize non-formal and informal learning and the dissemination of good practices,
- to enhance the international dimension of youth activities and capacity of youth workers (Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017)

A young person as defined by the Erasmus+ Programme, is between the ages of 13-30. For their participation in the program, it is not relevant whether and what they study or are trained in. This program provides opportunities to all young people and they can volunteer in or outside Europe or participate in a youth exchange abroad. (Erasmus+ Programme Guide, 2019)

4. The Erasmus+ Youth Exchanges project “Youth Exchanges Theory & Practice”

This project “Youth Exchanges Theory & Practice” has been co-founded by the Erasmus+ Youth in Action Programme. This is the component of the Erasmus+ Programme that is specially aimed at youth across Europe and supports their non-formal and informal learning.

Outcomes of the Erasmus+ Programme are classified by observing the needs of the youth. These are:

- improved learning performance,
- enhanced employability and improved career prospects,
- increased sense of initiative and entrepreneurship,
- increased self-empowerment and self-esteem,
- improved foreign language competencies,
- enhanced intercultural awareness,
- more active participation in society,
- better awareness of the European project and the EU values,
- increased motivation for taking part in future (formal/non-formal) education or training after the mobility period abroad (Erasmus+ Programme Guide, 2019, Perić Prkosovački, 2017)

These are all qualities and competences that are expected from young people in order to be productive and active members in their communities.

“Youth Exchanges Theory & Practice” was a two-year long Erasmus+ project of Volunteers’ center of Vojvodina (Serbia) in a co-operation with the partners from Germany (Europa Direkt e.V. Dresden) and France (Gwennili). The project was conducted from 2015 to 2017 in the field of providing mobility opportunities for young people from the three countries to gain intercultural experience and to become active citizens. The project focus/

target group was more specific - young vocational students. The idea of the project came from careful observation of European trends in education and labor markets. We have researched educational needs in the 21st century, tested it through implementation of two youth exchanges and trained a group of youth workers, teachers and social workers to improve their competencies to meet the educational needs of youth in the 21st century.

As a consequence of the research results, we have created the non-formal educational curriculum whose aim is to explore the potential of a 'youth exchange' theoretically and in practice as a methodology to provide young people with a quality mobility educational opportunity.

Results of the evaluation of the „Culture in Vocation“ exchange (Perić Prkosovački, 2017) have indicated significant traits, features and suggestions resulting from the exchange that have proven to be valuable and useful.

Most of the participants stressed as a positive result the possibility of getting to know other nations, their culture, traditions and customs (50% of answers). Participants reported a significant experience for professional training, experience sharing and exchange of knowledge and experience in the professional field (50% of answers). Participants also acknowledged the social importance as a 'nice thing' about the youth exchange. They cited as one of the significant advantages of the exchange, meeting new people and making new friends and creating international friendships.

When it comes to the importance of exchange („what is important for you?“) is the area of acquiring new knowledge and experiences primarily related to professional development. 42.31% gained significant new knowledge and skills in their own professional field. Participants believe, also, that they learned a lot about themselves and their personal development (23.08%).

In general, there are two facts of the „Culture in Vocation“ research. Firstly, intercultural relationships and the possibility of getting to know other nations, their culture, traditions and customs was assessed as the greatest personal gain. Secondly, participants see youth exchange as a useful experience for significant professional development. (Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017)

5. The methodology of youth exchanges

The methodology of youth exchanges is aiming at versatility, workshop-orientation and principally, actively acquiring knowledge. Activities may be themed if the exchange is following a specific program or participants choose a contemporary topic and are motivated to deal with that topic during the exchange. (Koskinen&Tossavainen,2004, Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017) The methodology of youth exchanges includes research activities, small group work, project group activities and outdoor activities.

Although there are a variety of group activities, working categories in youth exchanges are defined as:

- Meeting the group and developing good group dynamics - Team building activities
- Linguistic animations
- Themed activities
- Outdoor activities (Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017)

Andrew Malekoff's work with young people is recognized as one of the ways to promote the

development of critical thinking among young people. Working with young people allows young people to be well prepared for an active life in a democratic society, enabling them to cope better in situations that affect their lives or how to make a choice. (Malekoff, 2004, Glasser, 1999)

Young people need to feel they belong to a group, to have the support and understanding of their interests and needs. In order to achieve meaningful work with young people, it is necessary that they find themselves in the group, form close interpersonal group relationships, so they feel valuable and useful to the others. The aim should be: creation of good group dynamics, spontaneity and openness, welcoming, accepting and the establishment of a good atmosphere in the group. It is necessary for the group participants to find a common interest. (Malekoff, 2004) There are five causes of common interest:

Team building activities and activities for youth are constructive, and fun games help youth educators, group leaders and team members to develop a good platform for participants. Some of the types of team building activities include: communication activities, problem solving activities, planning and adaptability activities, trust-building activities. (Perić Prkosovački, et al, 2017)

Linguistic animations are daily exchange activities. This is an interactive activity in which language is used as a tool for intercultural learning. The goal for participants is to sensitize them to the languages of the participants of the exchange and experience language as a medium of communication.

Linguistic animation is a method that prompts communication, increases motivation to learn other languages and supports intercultural learning processes. This method is based on playful activities with different communication strategies - verbal, nonverbal or visual.

The Iceberg Model of Communication is often used by intercultural trainers to explain the communication. According to this model, one of the 'visible', external or conscious parts of culture is the language. The importance of language and youth exchanges seems to be of highest importance for young participants. When asked what they fear about the youth exchange, many of them name 'fear of being misunderstood' as one of the greatest. They fear that their foreign language skills are not developed enough to engage in communication with the peers from other countries. The first notion of communication for young people is 'verbal' communication. (Booth Sweeny, Meadows, 2010)

Themed activities are undertakings with a theme organized by the leaders or participants of the exchange. Themed activities could take different forms such as workshops, group work, research projects, a debate etc. on the actual work topic or on a subject that is of interest to the group.

Outdoor activities are the ones carried out in the open, include movement and exploration. They are mostly associated with sports activities and/or may include combining procedural work with groups. One of the combining techniques is exploring the environment or *Décryptage* (fr.). This is the first activity aimed at getting to know the surroundings and establishing contact with the local community. The name of this method is *Décodage*, a French word, which translated to English means 'Decoding'. The method teaches the young participants to observe and decode how their own culture shapes their views of the world around them.

'Decoding' culture consists of several phases:

From the description of surroundings that is going to be explored, the set up and explanation of learning goals, participants' work and discussion, to cultural awareness and critical thinking and reflection of young participants. (Perić Prkosovački et al, 2017)

6. Learning through the youth exchange spectrum

Knowledge society, Competence development or Lifelong learning are concepts of learning focused on global economic, environmental and cultural changes in recent decades. New educational concepts need to adapt innovation and new perspectives of learning.

Education system requirements have changed in recent decades. Including changes from passive to active self-directed learning processes and adjusting to a technology based society, the formal educational system should be open and flexible to other forms of learning.

The processes of learning outside formal systems are gaining in importance. Successful learning processes in the formal context of learning at school is not impossible. Time spent at schools is an insignificant period of time compared with the process of lifelong learning. Although significant, this is a very limited time period for learning. Much of the knowledge and competencies are acquired in extra-curricular activities.

There are many learning sources outside of school: place of work, through the media, evening courses, creative activities, youth work activities, exchanges, on the way to youth exchanges, volunteering, solving actual problems and learning from mistakes. Young people learn from instructors, colleagues, partners and competitors, parents, friends or children. All these forms of learning are taking place on a daily basis and outside formal educational institutions.

Awareness of the non-formal and informal process increased after the appearance of the EU Memorandum on Lifelong Learning (2000). Change is conditioned due to global

changes related to the development of information society and knowledge based societies. The new media mode allowed the direct transfer of data, the Internet enables constant access to the most current knowledge. In a working environment, people need to keep on top of their professional training in order to stay in touch with new and varied information technology.

This has had consequences for the formal educational system. A large quantity of knowledge and information is increasingly difficult to classify and track through formal frameworks.

Non-formal learning, including the youth exchanges, is any form of education that is conducted outside the formal educational system and serves to supplement formal education. Non-formal learning refers to acquiring knowledge, skills and competencies aimed to develop personal potential and values, interests and needs. Another name for this type of learning is non-institutional learning. (EU Memorandum on Lifelong Learning, 2000)

Non-formal learning activities include principles of active participation, relying on the experience of those who participate in them. In non-formal learning, those who participate in the learning activities ultimately create the outcomes of the process. Non-formal learning can be described as independent of educational institutions, but it does require a system or structure. The same can be found, for example, at a computer course, a study group or a foreign language course. It is not the opposite to the formal form of learning, instead, it could be a supplement to formal teaching.

Youth exchange is an instrument for non-formal learning. It contains planned and focused learning that is communicated through certain methods that are not characteristic for the formal education system. Similarly, in some areas of the exchange there is distinctive knowledge sharing and informal learning.

7. Conclusion

Intercultural learning is learning about different cultures, through interaction with members of diverse cultures. As such, intercultural learning is generally conducted within non-formal education frameworks, as a part of the curriculum or as a spontaneous consequence of programs that involve interculturalism as a secondary goal.

Challenging socio-economic conditions of global economic, environmental and cultural changes require different approaches in education. Students have active self-directed learning processes supported by educational concepts such as knowledge based society, competence development or lifelong learning.

Intercultural Vocational Exchange program helps students to overcome the gap between what they learn and what is expected from them in their professional life, including their needs and interests. Students, during the Intercultural Vocational Exchange, could reach the fitting balance between basic life skills, key specialized skills and intercultural skills.

Today, Youth Exchanges are defined, described, supported and promoted by Erasmus+ Programme of the European Commission. They are established as activities for young people that bring together a group of young people from two or more countries, providing them the opportunity to gain a new experience, learning about other cultures, socializing and traveling. Youth exchanges are viewed as part of formal and informal education, which use different and interesting activities.

The idea that drives intercultural exchange programme is the sharing of knowledge, skills and experience of the participants as a form of informal education with a special emphasis on vocational, experience and peer education.

Students find intercultural vocational exchange suitable and useful for their personal development. Intercultural relationships and the possibility of getting to know other nations, their culture, traditions and customs was assessed as the greatest personal gain. Students have defined the exchange as a useful experience for significant professional development, including knowledge and skills sharing and exchange in the professional field.

Participants also acknowledged the significance of the social aspect of youth exchange. They cited as one of the significant advantages of the exchange program, meeting new people and making new friends, equally reporting on the positive side of the exchange through making friends within their own country and in creating international friendships.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bennett, M. J. (2009): Defining, measuring, and facilitating intercultural learning: a conceptual introduction to the Intercultural Education double supplement. *Intercultural Education* Vol. 20, No. 1–13.

Booth Sweeny, L., Meadows, D. (2010): *The systems Thinking Playbook*. White River Junction, VT: Chelsea Green Publishing.

Dolo, L. (2000): *Individualna i masovna kultura*. Beograd: Klio.

Knežević-Florić, O. (2005): *Pedagogija razvoja*. Novi Sad: Filozofski fakultet, Katedra za pedagogiju.

European Commision. (2017): *Erasmus plus Programme guide*. Downloaded from: https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/sites/erasmusplus2/files/2017-erasmus-plus-programme-guide-v2_en.pdf [Jun, 15th, 2019]

European Commision. (2019): *Erasmus plus Programme guide*. Downloaded from: https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/erasmus-plus/sites/erasmusplus2/files/erasmus-plus-programme-guide-2019_en_2.pdf [Jun, 15th, 2019]

Commission Of The European Communities, (2000): A Memorandum on Lifelong Learning. Downloaded from: http://arhiv.acs.si/dokumenti/Memorandum_on_Lifelong_Learning.pdf [Jun, 28th, 2019]

Jovanov, I. (2013): Različite perpektive tumačenja interkulturalizma - Francuska-Nemačka, Hrvatska-Srbija. *Antropologija* 13, vol. 3 .UDK: 316.722(4), 109-130.

Koskinen, L., Tossavainen, K. (2004): Study abroad as a process of learning intercultural competence in nursing. *International journal of Nursing practice*, Vol. 10, No.3. 111-120. Doi: 10.1111/j.1440-172X.2004.00470.x.

Malekoff, A. (2004): *Group Work with Adolescents*. New York: The Guilford Publications, Inc

Milutinović, J., Zuković, S. (2008): Interkulturalno obrazovanje i reforma škole iz ugla kritičke pedagogije. Proceedings of papers, *Multikulturalno obrazovanje*. ur. Oljača, M. Novi Sad: Filozofski fakultet, Odsek za pedagogiju. 3, 59-75.

Glasser, W. (1999): *Nastavnik u kvalitetnoj školi*. Zagreb: Educa.

Perić Prkosovački, B., Prkosovački, V., Janković, T. (2017): *Youth Exchanges Theory & Practice, Prectical Manual*. Novi Sad. Volonterski centar Vojvodine. Downloaded from:

https://www.4shared.com/office/Sk73qA5mei/Profesionalci_prirucnik.html. [June, 16th, 2019]

Sandu, O. N., Lyamouri-Bajja, N. (2018): *T-Kit 4 Intercultural learning*. Council of Europe and European Commission. Downloaded from:

<https://pjp-eu.coe.int/documents/1017981/10762748/PREMS+042218+T-kit4+WEB.pdf/37396481-d543-88c6-dccc-d81719537b32> [July, 1st, 2019]

Rundstrom Williams, T. (2005): Exploring the Impact of Study Abroad on Students' Intercultural Communication Skills: Adaptability and Sensitivity. *Journal of Studies in International Education*, Vol. 9 No. 4. 356-371 Doi: 10.1177/1028315305277681

Zhukov. M. A., Schwieren S. (2017). International youth exchange and non-formal education, sinegretic efect. *Teadmine Ja Praktika Noorsootöö*, Tallinna Ülikooli. Trukikida: haridusteaduste instituudi elukestva- ja miiteformaalõppe suund, noorsootöö ja noorsootöö korraldus.

ABSTRACT

Performance pressure puts a big burden on people's shoulders. Adults have to stand the strain at work, while students have to fulfill the requirements at school. A segment of the students, who go to vocational training school, do not feel this burden, they can be characterised with a low level of learning motivation. Therefore, it is the teachers' task to involve these students in the classrooms activities.

Students in the 9th and 10th school years of vocational training school took part in the microresearch. The results obtained will hopefully answer the question of how the school or classroom environment affects learning motivation, which factors stimulate higher performance, encourage the learning of a given subject, and which factors orient the students to goals of avoiding learning. Furthermore, we receive a response to whether students prefer mastery goals or performance goals during their school years spent at secondary educational institutions.

Keywords: learning motivation, students' goals, vocational training school, mastery goals, performance goals

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